

Title:

Clinical Presentation, Treatment Response and Virology Outcomes of Women who Seroconverted in the Dapivirine Vaginal Ring Trials – The Ring Study and DREAM

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Key point summary:

Data from IPM 007 demonstrated that seroconversion during use of the dapivirine vaginal ring did not negatively affect clinical presentation or treatment outcome.

Mutation patterns at treatment failure were consistent with failure on an NNRTI-based regimen.

Abstract

Background

Participants who HIV seroconverted in The Ring Study, a Phase III trial of Dapivirine Vaginal Ring (DVR), or in the open-label extension trial DREAM, were offered enrollment in an observational cohort study (IPM 007) to assess clinical presentation and response to antiretroviral treatment (ART).

Methods

Participants' HIV infection was managed at local treatment clinics according to national treatment guidelines. IPM 007 study visits occurred 3 and 6 months after enrollment, and every 6 months thereafter. Assessments included plasma HIV-1 RNA, CD4+ T-cell counts, and recording of HIV/AIDS-associated events and ARV use. Post-hoc virology analyses were performed for participants identified with virologic failure.

Results

One-hundred-and-fifty-one of 179 eligible participants (84.4%) enrolled into IPM 007; 103 had previously received the DVR in the Ring or DREAM studies; 48 had received placebo in The Ring Study. HIV-1 RNA and CD4+ T-cell counts after 12 months' follow-up were similar for participants who used the DVR in The Ring Study and DREAM, compared to those who received placebo. Of the 78 participants with a study visit approximately 6 months after ART initiation, 59 (75.6%) had HIV-1 RNA <40 copies/mL (The Ring Study: placebo: 13/23; 56.5%; DVR: 32/39; 82.1%; DREAM [DVR]: 14/16; 87.5%). Post-hoc virology analysis

indicated that genotypic patterns observed at virologic failure were as expected of an NNRTI-based regimen.

Conclusions

Seroconversion during DVR use did not negatively affect clinical presentation or treatment outcome. Mutation patterns at virologic failure were in line with individuals failing an NNRTI-based regimen.

Introduction

A silicone matrix vaginal ring containing 25 mg dapivirine (an HIV-1 non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor [NNRTI]) reduced the risk of HIV-1 infection in women in two randomized placebo-controlled trials, The Ring Study (Protocol IPM 027) and ASPIRE (Protocol MTN-020) [1, 2]. In The Ring Study, the Dapivirine Vaginal Ring (DVR) demonstrated a statistically significantly reduced risk of HIV-1 infection compared to placebo, with an overall risk reduction of 35.1% (95% CI, 9.1 to 53.6) relative to placebo [3]. In the DREAM open-label extension trial (Protocol IPM 032), an HIV-1 incidence rate of 1.8 (95% CI, 1.1 to 2.9) per 100 person-years was observed, which is 62% lower than the simulated placebo rate based on bootstrap sampling of participants in the placebo group of The Ring Study, matched for research center (RC), age, and presence of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) at enrollment. The higher response rate in DREAM is most likely explained by increased product adherence due to knowledge of proven efficacy and safety [4].

Long-term follow-up of participants who acquired HIV in prevention trials is important for assessing if there are differences in antiretroviral (ARV) treatment response, and development of resistance post-ART initiation among participants previously exposed to an ARV or ARV-containing microbicide compared to placebo [5, 6]. This is particularly important when NNRTIs are used for prevention, as they generally have a lower genetic barrier to resistance compared to other ARV classes [7]. Indeed, several studies have shown that single dose nevirapine, used to prevent mother-to-child transmission of HIV-1, can select for NNRTI resistant virus [8, 9]. The results from the OCTANE trial demonstrated that archiving of virus with

resistant mutations might affect response during later exposure to the relevant ARV [10].

The proportions of participants with NNRTI resistance-associated mutations (RAMs) observed at seroconversion in both The Ring Study (14.8%) (Steytler et al., manuscript in preparation) and ASPIRE (11.0%) [11] were broadly consistent with a survey of transmitted HIV-1 drug resistance mutations in South Africa over a contemporaneous time period [12]. Although the proportions of participants with NNRTI RAMs in the DVR and placebo groups were similar, there was a statistically non-significant imbalance in the virus encoding E138A in The Ring Study [Steytler et al., manuscript in preparation]. No imbalance between study arms for virus encoding E138A was observed in the ASPIRE trial [11]. The E138A variant is a common polymorphism in subtype C HIV-1 isolates from southern Africa [13]. It is associated with potential or low-level resistance to the NNRTIs etravirine and rilpivirine (both close analogues of dapivirine), but it is not associated with resistance to efavirenz and nevirapine [13, 14, 15].

Here we describe the results of study IPM 007, an observational cohort study of HIV clinical presentation, response to ARV treatment and virologic outcomes in participants who seroconverted during The Ring Study and DREAM.

Methods

Study design and participants

Women who seroconverted (defined as previously described) [1, 2] in The Ring Study and DREAM were offered enrollment into IPM 007, a follow-up cohort study of

HIV infection. IPM 007 was an observational study and women were referred to local treatment clinics for management of their HIV infection and ARV treatment according to national treatment guidelines in place at the time.

IPM 007 was conducted from 4th October 2012 through 2nd May 2019 at the same RCs as The Ring Study and DREAM. Participant follow-up was expected to continue for at least 12 months after enrollment. Study visits were scheduled at months 3 and 6 after enrollment and every 6 months thereafter. As ARV treatment was initiated by local treatment clinics, independently of IPM 007, study visits and timepoints for assessment of ARV were not aligned and generally occurred later than defined response assessment points.

Samples for HIV-1 RNA and CD4+ T-cell count determination were taken at every visit, and data on HIV/AIDS-associated events recorded. ARV treatment data (initiation dates, regimen and adherence) based on participant report were recorded. Physical examinations were performed at all visits, but as no investigational product was used, adverse event monitoring or safety laboratory testing was not performed. Routine sample storage at each visit for potential HIV-1 susceptibility testing was not originally planned. However, storage was mandated in the IPM 007 Protocol Version 2.0 Amendment 2.0, dated 16 January 2017, which was fully implemented by September 2017.

The study was registered with ClinicalTrials.gov (NCT 01618058) and conducted in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki and International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use. All

local regulatory and legal requirements were followed. The study protocol was approved by independent ethics committees at all RCs. Written informed consent was provided by all participants.

Data presentation and analysis

Data are presented across five groups: The Ring Study treatment arm (DVR or placebo), DREAM participants (DVR), a total DVR group and all participants from both trials.

The study primary endpoint was HIV-1 RNA levels at 12 months after enrollment. Clinical presentation was evaluated through assessment of changes in WHO disease stage [16]. HIV-1 RNA levels and CD4+ T-cell count at 3 and/or 6 months post-enrollment and every 6 months thereafter, and time to ARV initiation were also determined. Response to ARV treatment was evaluated by assessing plasma HIV-1 RNA approximately 6, 12 and 24 months after treatment, maximizing visit and ARV commencement date alignment.

A post-hoc virology analysis defined the virology population as all enrolled participants with a visit after at least 6 months (180 days) of antiretroviral therapy. Virologic response was defined as HIV-1 RNA <200 copies/mL at all visits after 6 months' treatment; virologic failure included participants with no response, defined as HIV-1 RNA \geq 200 copies/mL after 180-days' self-reported uninterrupted treatment and those with rebound, defined as HIV-1 RNA \geq 200 copies/mL at any visit after achieving <200 copies/mL after at least 180 days of ARV treatment. Samples for HIV

susceptibility testing were available only if an analysis point was met at or after approximately September 2017.

Descriptive statistics were used for all analyses.

Virology methods

Population-based genotyping, using sequencing assays optimized for local HIV-1 subtypes, was performed at the Bio-Analytical Research Corporation laboratory in South Africa (BARC-SA) as previously described [17].

Testing was performed on all plasma samples with HIV-1 RNA >200 copies/mL, collected at the time of seroconversion from The Ring Study and DREAM, and at/after virologic failure (as defined for the post-hoc virology analysis) in IPM 007. Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) of available samples was performed at the Microbicide Trials Network (MTN) Virology Core Laboratory, Pittsburgh, using an Illumina platform-based NGS assay with unique molecular identifiers (UMI) to sequence reverse transcriptase (RT) codons 81 – 149 and 152 – 212 of the HIV-1 RT gene as previously described [5]. HIV-1 RT RAMs were identified using the Stanford HIV-1 Drug Resistance Database algorithm, Version 8.4 [8, 9].

Phenotypic susceptibility testing on full-length RT plasma-derived HIV-1 was also performed at the MTN Core Virology Laboratory using a validated laboratory-developed TZM-bl luciferase-based single cycle drug susceptibility assay as previously described [5]. Fold-change (FC) values were determined relative to a

parallel determination of 50% in vitro concentration (IC_{50}) of the NNRTIs dapivirine, nevirapine, efavirenz, etravirine and rilpivirine in a wild-type recombinant virus.

Results

Participant disposition

Of the 179 participants with confirmed HIV-1 seroconversion during The Ring Study (randomized 2:1 DVR: Placebo ring) and DREAM, 151 (84.4%) participants enrolled in IPM 007. Of these, 128 had seroconverted during The Ring Study (DVR: 80/151, 53.0%; placebo: 48/151, 31.8%) and 23 (23/151, 15.2%) during DREAM. The mean follow-up was 36.35 and 37.2 months for The Ring Study DVR and placebo participants, respectively; and 12.79 months for DREAM participants. Thirty-five (35/151, 23.2%) participants withdrew from the study early (Figure 1).

Study entry characteristics

The mean age of the 151 participants enrolled was 26.6 years, and the majority (140/151, 92.7%) were single. All participants were Black. Twenty-seven (17.9%) participants were on ARV treatment at enrollment into IPM 007 (Table 1). The mean time from seroconversion to IPM 007 enrollment was similar for all participant groups (The Ring Study: DVR: 134.2 days; placebo: 140 days; DREAM: 128.9 days).

Four participants did not have a genotype performed successfully during the parent trial. Virus from 25 of the remaining 147 (17.0%) participants had NNRTI RAMs detected prior to enrollment in IPM 007 and initiation of ARV treatment (NNRTI RAMs: The Ring Study: DVR: 17/78, 21.8%; placebo: 5/48, 10.4%; DREAM: 3/21, 14.3%). One participant had an accessory NRTI RAM (E44D) (Table 2).

Clinical presentation

One-hundred-and-thirty-three participants (88.1%) had a 12-month visit recorded, and HIV-1 RNA and CD4+ T-cell measurements were available for 132 participants. Overall (irrespective of ARV treatment), 42.9% participants who had used the DVR in The Ring Study had HIV-1 RNA <200 copies/mL at the 12-month follow-up visit, compared with 30.0% of participants who had used a placebo ring. Of those who had used the DVR in DREAM, 95.5% had HIV-1 RNA <200 copies/mL. Mean and median log-transformed HIV-1 RNA values were similar for the participants who used the DVR or a placebo ring in The Ring Study, with lower values recorded for participants who used the DVR in DREAM. All but two of the 64 participants who were not on ARVs at the 12-month follow-up visit had HIV-1 RNA \geq 200 copies/mL (Table 3). A sensitivity analysis of HIV-1 RNA concentrations 12 months after seroconversion in the Ring and DREAM trials, i.e., ignoring any delay in enrollment into IPM 007, showed similar results (see Supplementary Table S1).

Consistent with viral load findings, median CD4+ T-cell counts were similar for participants who used the DVR or placebo in The Ring Study, while the median was greater for DREAM participants (Table 4). During the study, the most advanced WHO stage recorded remained Stage 1 for >80% of participants, with no clinically significant differences between the groups (see Supplementary Table S2). The median time to ARV initiation was similar for participants who used the DVR or placebo ring in The Ring Study (482 and 496 days, respectively). Participants who used the DVR in DREAM initiated treatment sooner after seroconversion (median 48 days).

Response to ARV treatment

One-hundred-and-twenty-two (122/151, 80.8%) participants received ARVs at some point during IPM 007. All participants received an NNRTI-based regimen (120 participants received efavirenz, and two nevirapine). The proportion of participants with HIV-1 RNA <40 copies/mL and <200 copies/mL at approximately 6, 12 and 24 months after ARV initiation are summarized in Table 5. The response rate for The Ring Study DVR was not lower than that for the placebo group at any time point (Table 5). Participants who seroconverted in the DREAM trial had the highest response.

Virology analysis

At least 6 months' uninterrupted efavirenz-based ARV treatment was received by 113/151 (74.8%) enrolled participants (The Ring Study placebo: 34/48; DVR: 59/80; DREAM: 20/23); none changed therapy during the study. Virologic response was observed in 82/113 (72.6%) participants (The Ring Study: placebo: 20/34, 58.8%; DVR: 42/59, 71.2%; DREAM: 20/20, 100%). Fourteen of the 31 failures showed initial viral suppression with later rebound (placebo: 7/14, 50.0%; DVR: 7/17, 41.2%) and twelve of the failures showed virologic suppression at the termination visit (placebo: 5/14, 35.7%; DVR: 7/17, 41.2%).

Nineteen participants with ≥ 180 days' treatment had NNRTI RAMs at seroconversion (The Ring Study: DVR: n = 11; placebo: n = 5; DREAM: n = 3). Ten of the 14 (71.4%) DVR and 4 of the 5 (80.0%) placebo participants had HIV-1 RNA <200 copies/mL on study termination. This included 6 of 8 (75.0%) DVR participants

enrolled with virus encoding E138A as a lone NNRTI RAM. Viruses without NNRTI RAMs at seroconversion did not show any detrimental response among those with prior DVR use compared to placebo ring use (The Ring Study: DVR: 37/48, 77.1%; placebo: 17/31, 54.8%; DREAM: 17/17, 100%).

Of the failure viruses, population-based genotyping was available for 10/14 placebo- (4 failed prior to the protocol amendment) and 10/17 DVR-treated (4 failed prior to the protocol amendment and 3 had missing samples) participants. Although a slightly greater proportion of participants in The Ring Study DVR group had mutations at failure, numbers were too small to draw conclusions. Emerging mutations were consistent with failure during efavirenz use, with K103N the most prevalent (Table 6).

NGS analysis was successful in 9 samples from each group. In addition to the population-based genotyping-detected mutations, one each of minority species K103N (1% prevalence) and V108I (3% prevalence), and of K103N (33% prevalence), E138G (4% prevalence) and G190A (5% prevalence) were observed in the placebo and DVR groups, respectively.

Phenotypic susceptibility determinations were further limited by test failures (results: DVR: n = 6; placebo: n = 7). Fold-changes (FCs) did not indicate any reduction in dapivirine susceptibility compared to wild-type in viruses with none or one mutation, while virus with two mutations showed moderate FC (FC range DVR: 5.25 – 13.1; placebo: 2.13 – 41.7). One virus with 3 mutations (K103N, E138A, P225PH) from the DVR group had greater FC (>473) (see supplementary Table S4). Viruses with one or more mutation had high-level resistance to efavirenz and nevirapine (FC:

efavirenz: >19.8 – >21.9; nevirapine: 43.3 – >2102), but FC <10 for etravirine and rilpivirine (see supplementary Table S5).

Discussion

Evaluation of HIV-1 RNA, CD4+ T-cell counts and WHO disease stage showed no differences in participants who used the DVR in The Ring Study or DREAM, compared to those who used a placebo ring. HIV-1 RNA and CD4+ T-cell values were similar between the DVR and placebo groups from The Ring Study, while DREAM participants had lower HIV-1 RNA and higher CD4+ T-cell counts at the 12-month follow-up visit.

Time to initiation of ARV treatment was similar between the placebo and DVR groups from The Ring Study but was significantly shorter for DREAM participants. When looking at ARV response for participants with study visits at approximately 6, 12 and 24 months after treatment initiation, the proportion of participants with HIV-1 RNA <40 copies/mL and <200 copies/mL for the DVR groups was similar to, or higher than the proportions in the placebo group. This is consistent with the results of the MTN-015 study, which evaluated clinical progression and ARV responses in participants who seroconverted in the ASPIRE study [20]. The use of different cut-offs to define virologic suppression makes comparison across studies difficult; however, the proportion of participants with HIV-1 RNA <200 copies/mL compares favorably with data from the 2017 South African National HIV Survey which indicated that 87.3% of people living with HIV and receiving ARVs in South Africa had HIV-1 RNA <1000 copies/mL [21]. Data from a study in Uganda indicate that 95% of adults had HIV-1 RNA <1000 copies/mL after 12 months on first-line ARV regimens [22].

Overall, this indicates that participants who seroconverted in The Ring Study and DREAM, irrespective of treatment assignment, achieved ARV treatment responses in line with response rates reported in the general population of HIV-infected individuals in these regions.

The most likely explanation for the lower HIV-1 RNA and higher CD4+ T-cell counts at the 12-month follow-up visit, as well as improved ARV responses in DREAM participants, is the implementation of the universal test-and-treat (UTT) model in South Africa in September 2016 and in Uganda in February 2017. Prior to implementation of the UTT model, ARVs were initiated at a CD4+ count of less than 500 cells/ μ L [18, 19]. Due to the later trial initiation date of DREAM compared to The Ring Study, the implementation of the UTT strategy was in place for a greater proportion of the participants who seroconverted in DREAM.

The virologic findings indicate that DVR use at the time of infection was not detrimental to the later response to first-line NNRTI-based treatment during study IPM 007. Furthermore, while numbers were small, participants with virus-encoded mutations at seroconversion showed high proportions with virologic response. Importantly, the presence of E138A at seroconversion, the most prevalent mutation observed in The Ring Study, did not appear to reduce response to efavirenz-based regimens. The genotypic patterns, including additional mutations observed using NGS, observed at failure, were as expected of a first-generation NNRTI-based regimen, in most instances driven by K103N [8, 9]. Consistent with this, the failure viruses showed greater FC to efavirenz and nevirapine, than to dapivirine or the related drugs, etravirine and rilpivirine.

This study had several key limitations. In common with all follow-up cohort studies, selection processes (i.e., seroconversion during The Ring Study and DREAM, and enrollment in DREAM and IPM 007) may bias the population being observed. Furthermore, any differences between treatment groups in markers of clinical progression, time to treatment initiation and treatment response, are difficult to interpret, due to a change in the WHO ARV treatment guidelines to the UTT model during the study, the limited follow-up period, and the non-alignment of visits with time of seroconversion. For the virology analysis, the definition used to identify virologic response was applied retrospectively to reflect the more stringent endpoint used in the MTN-015 study [20]. The limited visit schedule, and challenges in aligning the visit schedule with timing of ARV initiation at external clinics, meant it was not possible to obtain timely confirmation of virologic failure and limited the number of available population-based genotype results. Additionally, dates of ARV initiation and adherence were based on participant reports and could not be verified. Finally, limited samples were available for NGS and phenotypic susceptibility analysis due to the late protocol amendment mandating the storage of samples. Despite these limitations, the as-observed analyses provide confidence that the prior use of DVR to reduce the risk of HIV-1 infection should not result in detrimental effects on clinical presentation or treatment outcomes during later treatment with first-generation NNRTI-based regimens. Although integrase inhibitor-based regimens are now preferred for initial treatment [23], NNRTIs might still be an option when integrase inhibitors cannot be used or after failure of earlier regimens. These results demonstrate that becoming HIV infected while using the DVR is unlikely to have any deleterious effect on management of HIV infection in the longer term.

Data Sharing

De-identified individual participant data from this study will be available to researchers with a methodologically sound proposal. Data requestors will need to sign a data access agreement. Publication concept proposal forms should be directed to mconradie@ipmglobal.org to gain access.

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Conflict of Interests

John Steytler, Jeremy Nuttall and Neliëtte van Niekerk were at the time of conduct of the study employees of the International Partnership for Microbicides. Elna van der Ryst, Charles Craig and Ben Van Baelen provided consulting services to International Partnership for Microbicides. All other authors declare no competing interests.

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Table 1. Participant Entry Characteristics

		Parent Trial			Total DVR n (%)	All Participants n (%)
		The Ring Study Placebo n (%)	The Ring Study DVR n (%)	DREAM DVR n (%)		
Number of participants enrolled		48	80	23	103	151
Age (years)	18 – 21	9 (18.8)	16 (20.0)	0	16 (15.5)	25 (16.6)
	>21 – 25	18 (37.5)	30 (37.5)	6 (26.1)	36 (35.0)	54 (35.8)
	>25 – 30	14 (29.2)	18 (22.5)	10 (43.5)	28 (27.2)	42 (27.8)
	>30 – 35	2 (4.2)	9 (11.3)	5 (21.7)	14 (13.6)	16 (10.6)
	>35	5 (10.4)	7 (8.8)	2 (8.7)	9 (8.7)	14 (9.3)
Marital Status	Married	3 (6.3)	4 (5.0)	1 (4.3)	5 (4.9)	8 (5.3)
	Single	44 (91.7)	75 (93.8)	21 (91.3)	96 (93.2)	140 (92.7)
	Separated	1 (2.1)	1 (1.3)	1 (4.3)	2 (1.9)	3 (2.0)
On ARVs ^a		2 (4.2)	8 (10)	17 (73.9)	25 (24.3)	27 (17.9)
DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring; n = number of participants with this observation; ARV = anti-retroviral drug Notes: ^a As reported by participant. Percentages are expressed as the percentage of the total number of participants enrolled in each treatment group.						

Table 2. Resistance-associated Mutations Detected Following HIV-1 Infection at Any Time Point After HIV-1 Infection in The Ring Study and DREAM

	Parent Trial			Total DVR (N = 103) n (%)	All Participants (N = 151) n (%)
	The Ring Study Placebo (N = 48) n (%)	The Ring Study DVR (N = 80) n (%)	DREAM DVR (N = 23) n (%)		
Participants with a genotype result	48 (100)	78 (97.5)	21 (91.3)	99 (96.1)	147 (97.4)
Participants with NNRTI Resistance Mutations					
None	43 (89.6)	61 (76.3)	18 (78.3)	79 (76.7)	120 (80.8)
Any	5 (10.4)	17 (21.3)	3 (13.0)	20 (19.4)	27 (16.6)
1 Mutation	3 (6.3)	15 (18.8)	3 (13.0)	18 (17.5)	21 (13.9)
2 Mutations	1 (2.1)	2 (2.5)	0	2 (1.9)	3 (2.0)
≥ 3 Mutations	1 (2.1)	0	0	0	1 (0.7)
Individual NNRTI Mutational Patterns					
A98G	1 (2.1)	2 (2.5)	1 (4.3)	3 (2.9)	4 (2.6)
K101E	1 (2.1)	0	1 (4.3)	1 (1.0)	2 (1.3)
K103N	1 (2.1)	2 (2.5)	0	2 (1.9)	3 (2.0)
E138A	0	10 (12.5)	1 (4.3)	11 (10.7)	11 (7.3)
G190GA	0	1 (1.3)	0	1 (1.0)	1 (0.7)
K101E, E138A	0	1 (1.3)	0	1 (1.0)	1 (0.7)
K103KN, V106VM	0	1 (1.3)	0	1 (1.0)	1 (0.7)
V106M, Y188C	1 (2.1)	0	0	0	1 (0.7)
V108I, Y181C, H221Y	1 (2.1)	0	0	0	1 (0.7)
Participants with NRTI Resistance Mutations					
E44D	0	1 (1.3)	0	1 (1.0)	1 (0.7)

Participants with PI Major Resistance Mutations					
M46L	0	2 (2.5)	1 (4.3)	3 (2.9)	3 (2.0)
<p>DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring; HIV-1 = human immunodeficiency virus type 1; N = number of participants enrolled; n = number of participants with this observation; NNRTI = non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor; NRTI = nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor; PI = protease inhibitor; RAM = resistance-associated mutation</p> <p>Notes: Percentages are expressed as the percentage of the total number of participants enrolled in each treatment group. Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 drug RAMs were defined according to the Stanford HIV-1 drug resistance database Version 8.4, dated 16 June 2017 [8, 9].</p>					

Table 3. HIV-1 RNA at the 12-Month Follow-up Visit

	Parent Trial			Total DVR (N = 103)	All Participants (N = 151)
	The Ring Study Placebo (N = 48)	The Ring Study DVR (N = 80)	DREAM DVR (N = 23)		
Participants with Month 12 follow-up after enrollment, n (%)	41 (85.4)	70 (87.5)	22 (95.7)	92 (89.3)	133 (88.1)
All participants – irrespective of ARV treatment					
N	40	70	22	92	132
HIV -1 RNA <40 copies/mL, n (%)	10 (25.0)	28 (40.0)	20 (90.9)	48 (52.2)	58 (43.9)
HIV-1 RNA ≥40 to <200 copies/mL, n (%)	2 (5.0)	2 (2.9)	1 (4.5)	3 (3.3)	5 (3.8)
HIV-1 RNA ≥200 copies/mL, n (%)	28 (70.0)	40 (57.1)	1 (4.5)	41 (44.6)	69 (52.3)
Log HIV-1 RNA, Mean	3.47	2.98	1.76	2.69	2.92
Log HIV-1 RNA, Median	3.99	2.95	1.59	1.59	2.68
Log HIV-1 RNA, Range	1.6 - 5.8	1.6 - 5.6	1.6 - 5.0	1.6 - 5.6	1.6 - 5.8
Participants not on ARV treatment ^a					
N	25	37	2	39	64
HIV -1 RNA <40 copies/mL, n (%)	0	1 (2.7) ^b	1 (50)	2 (5.1)	2 (3.1)
HIV-1 RNA ≥40 to <200 copies/mL, n (%)	0	0	0	0	0
HIV-1 RNA ≥200 copies/mL, n (%)	25 (100)	36 (97.3)	1 (50.0)	37 (94.9)	62 (96.9)

Log HIV-1 RNA, Mean	4.24	4.03	3.28	4.00	4.09
Log HIV-1 RNA, Median	4.23	4.07	3.28	4.07	4.16
Log HIV-1 RNA, Range	2.9 – 5.8	1.6 – 5.6	1.6 – 5.0	1.6 – 5.6	1.6 – 5.8
<p>ARV = antiretroviral; DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring; HIV-1 = human immunodeficiency virus type 1; N = number of participants enrolled; n = number of participants with this observation; RNA = ribonucleic acid</p> <p>Notes:</p> <p>^a As reported by the participant.</p> <p>^b Participant is a suspected elite controller: HIV-1 RNA remained <40 copies/mL throughout.</p> <p>Percentages for the participants with 12 months of follow-up are based on the number of participants enrolled in each treatment group. All other percentages are expressed as the percentage of the total number of participants with plasma HIV-1 RNA levels at 12 months in each treatment group.</p>					

Table 4. CD4+ T-Cell Counts at the 12-Month Follow-up Visit

	Parent Trial			Total DVR (N = 103)	All Participants (N = 151)
	The Ring Study Placebo (N = 48)	The Ring Study DVR (N = 80)	DREAM DVR (N = 23)		
Participants with Month 12 follow-up after enrollment, n (%)	41 (85.4)	70 (87.5)	22 (95.7)	92 (89.3)	133 (88.1)
All participants – irrespective of ARV treatment					
N	40	70	22	92	132
CD4+ T-cell count <200 cells/μL, n (%)	2 (5.0)	0	0	0	2 (1.5)
CD4+ T-cell count 200 to 500 cells/μL, n (%)	20 (50.0)	29 (41.4)	2 (9.1)	31 (33.7)	51 (38.6)
CD4+ T-cell count >500 cells/μL, n (%)	18 (45.0)	41 (58.6)	20 (90.9)	61 (66.3)	79 (59.8)
Median CD4+ T-cell count (cells/μL) (Range)	486 (199 – 1219)	563 (251 – 1378)	755.5 (357 – 1137)	605.5 (251 – 1378)	570 (199 – 1378)
Participants not on ARV treatment ^a					
N	25	37	2	39	64

CD4+ T-cell count <200 cells/ μ L, n (%)	1 (4.0)	0	0	0	1 (1.6)
CD4+ T-cell count 200 to 500 cells/ μ L, n (%)	15 (60.0)	19 (51.4)	1 (50.0)	20 (51.3)	35 (54.7)
CD4+ T-cell count >500 cells/ μ L, n (%)	9 (36.0)	18 (48.6)	1 (50.0)	19 (48.7)	28 (43.8)
Median CD4+ T-cell count (cells/ μ L) (Range)	477.0 (199 – 821)	497.0 (251 – 1378)	530 (368 – 692)	497.0 (251 – 1378)	493.5 (199 – 1378)
<p>ARV = antiretroviral; DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring; HIV-1 = human immunodeficiency virus type 1; N = number of participants enrolled; n = number of participants with this observation; CD = cluster of differentiation</p> <p>Notes: ^a As per participant report. Percentages are expressed as the percentage of the total number of participants enrolled in each treatment group.</p>					

Table 5. Response to ARV Treatment

	Parent Trial			Total DVR	All Participants
	The Ring Study Placebo	The Ring Study DVR	DREAM DVR		
Participants with follow-up approximately 6 months after ARV therapy initiation ^a					
N	23	39	16	55	78
HIV-1 RNA <40 copies/mL, n (%)	13 (56.5)	32 (82.1)	14 (87.5)	46 (83.6)	59 (75.6)
HIV-1 RNA ≥40 to <200 copies/mL, n (%)	2 (8.7)	2 (5.1)	1 (6.3)	3 (5.5)	5 (6.4)
HIV-1 RNA ≥200 copies/mL, n (%)	8 (34.8)	5 (12.8)	1 (6.3)	6 (10.9)	14 (17.9)
Participants with follow-up approximately 12 months after ARV therapy initiation ^a					
N	27	49	19	68	95
HIV-1 RNA <40 copies/mL, n (%)	21 (77.8)	40 (81.6)	18 (94.7)	58 (85.3)	79 (83.2)
HIV-1 RNA ≥40 to <200 copies/mL, n (%)	0	2 (4.1)	1 (5.3)	3 (4.4)	3 (3.2)
HIV-1 RNA ≥200 copies/mL, n (%)	6 (22.2)	7 (14.3)	0	7 (10.3)	13 (13.7)
Participants with follow-up approximately 24 months after ARV therapy initiation ^a					
N	26	39	4	43	69
HIV-1 RNA <40 copies/mL, n (%)	16 (61.5)	31 (79.5)	4 (100)	35 (81.4)	51 (73.9)

HIV-1 RNA ≥ 40 to < 200 copies/mL, n (%)	1 (3.8)	2 (5.1)	0	2 (4.7)	3 (4.3)
HIV-1 RNA ≥ 200 copies/mL, n (%)	9 (34.6)	6 (15.4)	0	6 (14.0)	15 (21.7)
<p>ARV = antiretroviral; DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring; HIV-1 = human immunodeficiency virus type 1; N = number of participants enrolled; n = number of participants with this observation; RNA = ribonucleic acid</p> <p>Notes: ^a As per participant report. Percentages are expressed as the percentage of the total number of participants with plasma HIV-1 RNA levels in each visit/treatment group.</p>					

Table 6. Summary of NNRTI and NRTI RAMs on Failure in The Ring Study ^a

	The Ring Study Placebo	The Ring Study DVR
Population-based genotyping (N)	10	10
With no mutations, n (%)	4 (40.0)	2 (20.0)
With any mutations, n (%)	6 (60.0)	8 (80.0)
With new NNRTI RAMs, n (%)	4 (40.0)	6 (60.0)
Plus NRTI RAMs, n (%)	3 (30.0)	2 (20.0)
Emergent major mutations ^b		
L100I	1/1	0/0
K101E	0/0	1/1
K103N	3/5	4/5
V106M	0/1	2/2
E138A	0/0	0/2
G190A	0/0	1/1
M230L	1/1	0/0
DVR = dapivirine vaginal ring; NNRTI = non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitor; NRTI = nucleoside/tide reverse transcriptase inhibitor; RAM = resistance-associated mutation ^a NNRTI and NRTI patterns are provided in Supplementary Table S3. ^b Human immunodeficiency virus type 1 drug RAMs were defined according to the Stanford HIV-1 drug resistance database Version 8.4, dated 16 June 2017 [8, 9].		

Figure 1. Participant Disposition

Figure 1 Legend:

N = number of participants

Percentages for the primary reasons for participant discontinuation from the study are based on the number of participants who discontinued participation from the study early in each treatment group.

All other percentages are expressed as the percentage of the total number of participants enrolled in each treatment group.